

OSCAR

Open Science Clusters' Action
for Research & Society

mTeSS-X Documentation

Deliverable D4: Onboarding guides, user guides, training materials, and FAQs for developers and service providers to integrate their services and metadata into the mTeSS platform to facilitate onboarding of new communities and content providers

December 2025, version 1.0

Authors: Phil Reed, Finn Bacall, Munazah Andrabi, Carole Goble (UNIMAN-UK), Oliver Knodel, Martin Voigt (HZDR-DE), Kenneth Rioja (CERN), the mTeSS-X Focus Group

Introduction and scope.....	1
Scope of the deliverable.....	2
Dedicated documentation for the TeSS platform.....	2
Motivation for change.....	2
Design of TeSS Platform documentation.....	2
Broader community engagement and identity across domains.....	3
Conclusions and next steps.....	4

Introduction and scope

To overcome fragmentation of training resources across Research Infrastructures (RIs) and the Science Clusters, the [mTeSS-X project](#) aims to enhance the existing [ELIXIR TeSS platform](#), to build an aggregator for training portals like ELIXIR TeSS and [PaNOSC training portals](#), to natively support federation. Such a fully-featured open-source multi-tenanted training platform is expected to be an innovation for building a federation of portals to:

- help break down barriers between thematic communities,
- and promote FAIR and open training.

The project strives to support the federation of training catalogues using a multi-tenancy (multi-space) approach, and enabling cross-instance content exchange. This will allow RIs and their communities to maintain tailored catalogues with distinct identities, while simultaneously benefiting from a shared global pool of resources.

Scope of the deliverable

This document describes the new documentation resource for the TeSS Platform, the audience it serves, and how the resource will be maintained.

Dedicated documentation for the TeSS platform

Motivation for change

Previously, the user documentation for TeSS was provided under the 'About' page within the platform website itself, for each instance of TeSS (such as [ELIXIR TeSS](#), [PaN Training](#) and [DReSA](#)). This embedded location had the advantage that text could be customised or localised for each instance. There were several disadvantages:

- **Highly technical environment:** Creating and modifying documentation content required the installation of the full TeSS application code base, Rails and Docker.
- **Difficult templating:** Documents were written in Ruby, ERB and HTML, with relatively complicated templating language.
- **Slow release schedule:** Changes were not published to the users until each TeSS instance administrator updated to a newer release of the TeSS platform.

Several standalone, dedicated platforms were [considered](#), all designed specifically for documentation, with easy hosting and collaboration in mind. We selected [Jupyter Book](#) version 1 (the latest version at the time), as used by [IBISBA Workshops](#). This Jupyter Book platform is free and open source, built on Python, and doesn't need a Docker image (therefore much faster to run locally). The front-end supports light and dark views, has an integrated search feature, and can be easily customised through additional CSS and Javascript.

Design of TeSS Platform documentation

The documentation is available at <https://elixirtess.github.io/docs/>, with source code at <https://github.com/ElixirTeSS/docs>. It is written for the Trainee, Trainer, Curator, Space Curator, Training Coordinator, Space Manager and Content Provider **user personas identified** in Deliverable [D1 mTeSS-X Requirements](#). We include some content for the Developer user

persona, however, the more detailed [technical installation guidance](#) remains hosted in GitHub with the codebase.

The new documentation is intended to provide help and information on how to use a training registry created on the TeSS platform. It includes all four kinds of documentation content: **tutorials**, **how-to guides**, **reference** and **explanation** ([Diátaxis, 2022](#)). There are notes throughout to indicate variation between instances of TeSS, (though this is not intended to be comprehensive). The materials are presented in the following sections:

- **Overview** (what is TeSS, global usage, definitions)
- **Search** (browse and filter all kinds of content)
- **Account creation** (user and content providers registration)
- **Space creation** (how and when to request a space, alternatives)
- **Content registration** (manual upload, automatic ingestion)
- **Exchange** (share materials between spaces and instances)
- **Developers** (how to add a TeSS widget to your site, use the API)

The materials are written in **Markdown**, a popular and simple language, with additional template syntax from [Sphinx](#). The editorial process is similar to the main TeSS codebase, where contributors can raise Issues and make pull requests on GitHub, or more simply make suggestions at the TeSS Club community calls. There is a GitHub project board to prioritise and manage the ongoing development of the documentation, with responsibility shared across the TeSS development team and led by the community manager.

Broader community engagement and identity across domains

The community of TeSS users began within ELIXIR, the European life science research infrastructure. The regular TeSS Club call is accompanied by a channel in the ELIXIR Slack

space, where anybody in an ELIXIR member institution can ask questions to other TeSS users at any time. A **new Slack space** was created called [TeSS Platform](#), designed to operate across all research domains. The TeSS Club channel is replicated in the new Slack space, and developer and project management discussions have moved over into private channels.

Further, a **new visual identity** was created for the TeSS Platform, to better distinguish the TeSS name and logo from the ELIXIR portal. There is a logo for the TeSS Platform with intersecting square graphical features to represent the spaces and exchange features developed as part of the project. The primary and secondary colours of orange and blue are lifted from the ELIXIR TeSS visual identity for the sake of continuity and accessibility.

Conclusions and next steps

The mTeSS-X project represents a significant advancement in the federation of training catalogues across scientific domains, Research Infrastructures and training portals. Through a domain agonistic review, the project documentation has been successfully launched, ensuring that practical usage needs of both trainers and trainees are met.

Looking ahead, we intend to continue active engagement with the diverse user community to build on the existing collection of tutorials, how-to guides, reference and explanatory materials. This will be done via the focus group meetings which continue to be held every three months throughout the duration of the project. The next such meeting scheduled for 2026-01-27 will provide a demonstration of the multi-spaces and exchange feature implementations and gather feedback from the community. In the meeting, we also plan to discuss the metadata exchange work, in the context of an EOSC federated training catalogue.

This work was supported through the Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society (OSCARS) European project under grant agreement N°101129751.